

CURRENT STATE AND DYNAMICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF STOCK MARKET TURNOVER

Kakhramon Chinkulov

Associate Professor of the Department of "Finance", PhD, Tashkent Financial Institute. E-mail: kahramon114@yahoo.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8038781>

Abstract. The thesis analyzes the volume of the total issue of stocks and the dynamics of exchange turnover, compares the share of exchange turnover in GDP in Uzbekistan and abroad, indicates the reason for the low liquidity of the exchange, developed scientific and practical conclusions and proposals.

Keywords: stocks, joint-stock company, IPO, SPO, issue, share capital, stock market, securities market, financial market, exchange turnover.

At the level of the head of state, attention is paid to a sharp increase in the turnover of the stock market. In particular, the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" was adopted by the relevant decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The 27th goal of this strategy is: "In order to increase financial resources in the economy, increase the turnover of the stock market from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars in the next 5 years, gradually liberalize the movement of capital in our country and sell large enterprises and their shares including privatization through the stock exchange" defined [1.].

Although the importance of joint-stock companies in the national economy is great, the dynamic analysis of subsequent years confirms that their contribution to the gross domestic product is declining; Despite the observed growth rates, the fact that it is at a low level compared to the GDP growth rate creates the need for decision-making aimed at their sustainable economic development [2.].

As we know from practice, the stock market occupies the most important place in the structure of the stock market. Unlike other securities, shares represent ownership of property. Analyzing the dynamics of this financial instrument, we can see whether property relations have increased or decreased.

According to foreign economist Ya.M. Mirkin, "The main purpose of the stock market is to finance economic growth and innovation. Stock market should become a mechanism for attracting investment in the real sector" [3.].

The stability of market relations in the country can be assessed through the securities market (SM). "... depending on the state of the stock market, one

can think about the extent to which the decision-making process of market relations becomes active" [4.].

Therefore, we can also analyze the current state of the turnover of the stock market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and give a real assessment of the state of the country's securities market.

We can analyse the total capitalization of the stock market and the ratio of the total market capitalization of the stock market to GDP in 2020-2022.

The total market capitalization of the stock market of our republic in 2022 amounted to 11.33%. While the world average for this indicator is 117.7% [5.]. Therefore, we cannot positively evaluate the current state of the capitalization level of the stock market. Because today the level of capitalization of joint-stock companies (JSC) of our republic is 10 times lower than the world average in this regard.

Also, although the issuance of shares tends to increase, the share of the stock market is very small. This can also be seen from the data in Table 1.

Table 1.

Comparative indicator of GDP, the volume of the total issue of shares and the dynamics of the stock market turnover [6.]

INDICATORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
The volume of GDP, in trillion soum	144,55	177,15	210,18	242,49	302,54	406,65	510,12	580,20	734,6	888,34
The total volume of share issue, in trillion soum	10,25	12,72	16,55	30,46	48,63	59,40	99,20	149,50	153,10	166,74
Amount of exchange turnover, in billion soums	93,2	97,6	161,0	299,8	298,6	687,3	438,82	578,15	126,05	481,62
Share of exchange turnover in GDP, in %	0,06	0,06	0,08	0,12	0,10	0,17	0,09	0,10	0,17	0,54
Share of exchange turnover in the total volume of issue, in %	0,91	0,77	0,97	0,98	0,61	1,16	0,44	0,39	0,82	2,88

From the data in Table 1 shows that the share of stock market turnover in GDP was very small and increased over the period under review from 0.06% to 0.54%. However, according to the World Bank, this figure is 133.8% in South

Korea, 27.1% in Japan, 48.7% in Turkey, 43.8% in Germany, 39% in the Russian Federation, 29% in Kazakhstan, 7% in Belarus [7].

Although the total volume of shares issued in our country tends to grow, in 2022 it will reach 166.74 trillion. UZS, the turnover of these shares on the stock exchange fluctuated for a number of years between 0.39% and 2.88%. In other words, only 2.88 percent of the total issuance of shares will be traded on the exchange in 2022. This is a very low figure. Of course, we cannot evaluate this situation positively.

According to the author, the main reason for the very low share of exchange turnover in relation to GDP and the total volume of emission is the extremely high share of the state in the authorized capital of JSCs.

As of January 1, 2023, the state's share is 85.3%, including the share of economic management bodies in the authorized capital of JSC [7.]. That is, we can say that 85.3% of the authorized capital is under the control of the state, in a "frozen" state. It cannot be a freely traded resource for the stock market. 4.7% of the shares are in the process of placement. Only 10% of the shares belong to other shareholders. Theoretically, only 10% of the authorized capital of a JSC of our republic can be a freely tradable resource on the stock market. In practice, as mentioned above, the stock market turnover is much lower (the share of the stock market turnover in the total issue volume in 2022 was only 2.88%).

We cannot evaluate this situation positively. It is more beneficial for the economy of our country if the share of state and economic management bodies decreases in the number of JSCs and in the authorized capital, while the share of private investors, on the contrary, increases.

Also, according to the results of studies conducted in the world, the efficiency of large public and mixed corporations is much lower than that of private corporations.

In this regard, it is important to find and implement the "golden mean". That is, it is necessary to choose such a level of the state's share that, on the one hand, the interests of the state are taken into account, and on the other hand, the effectiveness of the JSC's activities should be ensured.

Studies have shown that the main cause of stock volatility is an unsustainable share capital structure. Most of the shares belong to state and economic management bodies. A radical reduction in the state's share in the authorized capital of JSCs will help solve this problem.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 2022 No. PP-90 "On additional measures to introduce effective mechanisms to

support the capital market” was adopted. According to this decision, from April 1, 2022, local issuers have been granted the right to place their shares on foreign stock markets or simultaneously on local and foreign stock exchanges on the recommendation of the underwriter after the initial placement of their shares on RSE ‘Tashkent’. Of course, we hope that this decision will facilitate an international IPO or SPO.

In general, as a result of the study, the following conclusions and proposals were made:

1. In the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", it is determined to increase the turnover of the stock market from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars by the end of 2026. At the end of 2022, the turnover of the stock market will amount to 429 million dollars. So, in this regard, reaching the volume specified in the Development Strategy requires decisive efforts from us.

2. The share of exchange turnover in the GDP of Uzbekistan has a growing trend and at the end of 2022 amounted to 0.54%. However, according to the World Bank, this figure is 29%, for example, in neighboring Kazakhstan.

3. According to the results of our study, the main reason for the inactivity of shares on the stock market of our republic (low turnover of the stock market) is the unreasonable composition of the total authorized capital. Most of the shares belong to state and economic management bodies (85.3% as of January 1, 2023) and cannot be circulated at all. Ultimately, as we noted above, the reduction of the state's share will create the possibility of increasing the turnover of the stock market. However, it is fundamentally important to pay special attention to the transparent and fair conduct of privatization.

Bibliography:

1. "New Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", approved by Appendix 1 to Decree No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>.
2. Karlibaeva R.Kh. Ways of effective organization of the financial management system in joint-stock companies. Abstract diss ... Doctor of Economics. - Tashkent, 2018. - P.15.
3. Mirkin Ya.M. Thirty theses (key ideas for the development of the stock market). // Securities Market, 2000. - No. 11.-P.12.
4. Karimov I.A. Towards security and sustainable development. -T.: Uzbekistan, 1995.—P.170.
5. Obidov A. Development of capital markets in Uzbekistan. International financial and banking forum. - Tashkent, 2019. - March 27-31.

6. Compiled by the author on the basis of information from the RSE "Tashkent" and the State Statistics Committee.
7. Chinkulov K. Functions of joint stock companies in the economy and improvement of their financing. Journal of Innovations in Economy. 2021;4(8):26-34.

